

The Impact of Self Directed Learning and Digital Literacy for Study Result Pengelolaan Bisnis Ritel Subject Grade XI BDP SMK Negeri 1 Medan 2022/2023

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to find out the influence of Self Directed Learning and Digital Literacy on the Learning Results of Class XI BDP SMK Negeri 1 Medan. The population in this study is the entire student class XI BDP SMK State 1 Medan T.A 2022/2023 which totaled 66 students. The sampling technique was carried out using total samplings to obtain a sample of 66 students. In the meantime, for the collection of research data obtained from elevators and lists of student values. The result of the double linear regression test showed the constant value (a) of 4.019, the self-directed learning variable regression coefficient value of 0.623, then the Digital Literation variabel regression factor of 0.362. It was concluded that Self Directed Learning and Digital Literacy had a significant impact on Retail Business Management Lesson Results in Class XI BDP SMK State 1 Medan T.A 2022/2023.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a conscious and planned endeavor to create an atmosphere of learning and learning processes so that the student actively develops his or her potential to have the spiritual powers of religion, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble morals, and skills necessary to him or her and society. Maintenance of education is carried out in order to empower and enable students to live their lives. It is in accordance with the general provisions of the Undang-Undang Sistem Pendidikan Nasional Tahun 2003 pasal 1 ayat 1, which explain that education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning environment and learning process so that the student actively develops his or her potential to possess spiritual powers of religion, self-control, personality, intelligence, and noble morality, as well as the skills required of himself, society, nation, and religion. From the results of the pre-observations that the researchers have carried out, it appears that there are still students who have not been able to create a conducive learning environment, cannot make a good study schedule, cannot determine a good learning objective, do not have the desire to learn, cannot overcome their learning obstacles well, are not able to use the learning resources properly, and cannot evaluate their learning process.

One of the external factors that influence learning outcomes is digital literacy. Digital literacy is the ability of a person to understand and use technology and information from digital devices effectively and efficiently in a variety of contexts, such as academic, career, and day-to-day activities. (2017:65). In the context of education, good digital literacy also plays a role in developing a person's knowledge of a particular subject by encouraging the curiosity and creativity that students have. In order to be able to harmonize the ability to learn independently with the availability of abundant learning resources on the Internet, a student should have the capacity to operate digital technology to the maximum. Maria (2018:2).

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Study for the result of Pengelolaan Bisnis Ritel Subject

A learning outcome is one that indicates an achievement, a degree of success in achieving a goal, or the result of an effort of learning that has been performed optimally by a person. According to Monika and Dkk (2017:110), learning results are one way to measure how well students understand learning. The results of learning include knowledge, skills, attitudes, and mental habits developed and brought about by students. According to Widodo's opinion, dkk (2013:34) argues that "the learning results are patterns of actions, values, understanding, attitude, appreciation, and skills.

Self Directed Learning

Self-directed learning, or self-directed learning, is a way of learning in which students consciously control and carry out their learning activities. This means that students have their own initiative in conducting learning activities. Start by preparing the learning so that it's comfortable in the learning process. Whatever this place should be owned by every individual besides getting knowledge from the school.

Digital Literacy

Kahar (2018:2) argues that "digital literacy is the ability to use digital technology to understand, evaluate, use, and create information." In line with Nurnannah's opinion, dkk (2017) argued that literacy was the capacity to understand and use information in various formats that came from various digital sources displayed through computers.

Wahyudi (2017:18) argues that "digital literacy is part of the literacy of information as a whole. Digital literacy encompasses two concepts: the web and

search engines."More in depth is illustrated by Kajin (2018:135), who states that "digital literature consists of information literacy, media literacy, and ICT literacy."

METHODS

To obtain the data from the field as the material for this writing, it is necessary to use the appropriate data collection methods. The data collection technique used in this study was quantitative, with a sample of 66 students from Grade XI BDP SMK Negeri 1 Medan. The technique used in this study is total sampling.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Result

Self Directed Learning

Table 4.5
Analysis of Self Directed Learning

Interval	Kategori
1,00-1,75	Not Good
1,76-2,49	Good Enough
2,50-3,25	Good
3,26-4,00	Very Good

Table 4.6
Frequency Distribution for the Answer: Self-Directed Learning (X1)

No. Item	SS=4		S=3		TS=2		STS=1		Jumlah		Rata-Rata	Kategori
	F	SC	F	SC	F	SC	F	SC	F	SC		
1	21	84	40	120	5	10	0	0	66	214	3,242	Good
2	13	52	40	120	12	24	1	1	66	197	2,984	Good
3	15	60	38	114	12	24	1	1	66	199	3,015	Good
4	4	16	14	42	40	80	8	8	66	146	2,212	Good Enough
5	24	96	32	96	7	14	3	3	66	209	3,166	Good
6	1	4	13	39	29	58	23	23	66	124	1,878	Good Enough
7	16	64	37	111	11	22	2	2	66	199	3,015	Good
8	5	20	17	51	28	56	16	16	66	143	2,166	Good Enough
9	12	48	12	36	14	28	5	5	66	117	1,772	Good Enough
10	5	20	19	57	31	62	11	11	66	150	2,272	Good Enough
11	13	52	35	105	16	32	2	2	66	191	2,893	Good
12	11	44	9	27	35	70	11	11	66	152	2,303	Good Enough
13	17	68	39	117	9	18	1	1	66	204	3,090	Good
14	5	20	24	72	34	68	3	3	66	163	2,469	Good Enough
15	17	68	41	123	8	16	0	0	66	207	3,136	Good
	Total										2615	

	Rata-Rata Keseluruhan			2,640	Good
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F = Frekuensi

SC= Skor

Based on the table 4.8 presented, the average score is 2,640 in the category "Good." This indicates that self-directed learning can be said to be "Good".

Digital Literacy

Table 4. 9
Analysis Digital Literacy (X2)

Interval	Kategori
1,00-1,75	Not Good
1,76-2,49	Good Enough
2,50-3,25	Good
3,26-4,00	Very Good

Tabel 4. 10
Distribusi Frekuensi Jawaban Angket Literasi Digital (X2)

No. Item	SS = 4		S = 3		TS = 2		STS = 1		JUMLAH		RATA- RATA	KET
	F	SC	F	SC	F	SC	F	SC	F	SC		
1	28	112	24	72	13	26	1	1	66	211	3,196	Good
2	32	128	28	84	5	10	1	1	66	223	3,378	Very Good
3	33	132	31	93	2	4	0	0	66	229	3,469	Very Good
4	26	104	38	114	2	4	0	0	66	222	3,363	Very Good
5	24	96	39	117	3	6	0	0	66	219	3,318	Very Good
6	24	96	33	99	1	2	1	1	66	198	3	Good
7	28	112	33	99	5	10	0	0	66	221	3,348	Very Good
8	19	76	42	126	5	10	0	0	66	212	3,212	Good
9	27	108	31	93	6	12	2	2	66	215	3,257	Very Good
10	26	104	37	111	3	6	0	0	66	221	3,348	Very Good
11	25	100	36	108	4	8	1	1	66	217	3,287	Very Good
12	28	112	32	96	6	12	0	0	66	220	3,333	Very Good
13	22	88	39	117	5	10	0	0	66	215	3,257	Very Good
14	26	104	31	93	8	16	1	1	66	214	3,242	Good
15	21	84	41	123	4	8	0	0	66	215	3,257	Good
16	23	92	35	105	7	14	1	1	66	212	3,212	Good
17	27	108	36	108	3	6	0	0	66	222	3,363	Very Good
18	26	104	39	117	1	2	0	0	66	223	3,378	Very Good
19	28	112	34	102	4	8	0	0	66	222	3,363	Very

												Good
20	24	96	35	105	7	14	0	0	66	215	3,257	Good
			JUMLAH						4346			

Study for The Result

Table 4. 13
Tendence Level of The Variable Value of The Study for the Result (Y)

Nilai Interval	Frekuensi Absolut	Frekuensi Relatif	Kategori
> 80,61	32	48,48%	Very Good
61,25 – 80,61	3	4,55%	Good
41,89 – 61,25	27	40,91%	Good Enough
< 41,89	4	6,06%	Not Good
Total	66	100%	

Sumber: Data Angket Penelitian Hasil Belajar

According to table 4.14, the variable Learning Outcome includes the following categories: very high 48,48%, high 4,55%, low 40,91%, and very low 6,06%. So it can be concluded that, in general, the learning outcomes of Class XI BDP SMK State 1 Field are very good.

Double Linear Regression Analysis Test

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.019	12.577		.320	.750
	X1	.623	.123	.508	5.068	.000
	X2	.362	.125	.292	2.910	.005

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Sumber: Pengolahan Data dengan Program SPSS 25

From the data processing results in the table above, the regression equation model is obtained as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 4,019 + 0,623 (X1) + 0362 (X2) + e$$

Keterangan:

Y = Study for the result

X1 = Self Directed Learning

X2 = Digital Literacy

From the data processing results in the table above, the regression equation model is obtained as follows:

1. The constant value (a) of 4,019 can be interpreted as meaning that Pengelolaan Bisnis Ritel Subject in Grade XI BDP 2022/2023 Year (Y) will be worth 4.019 when self-directed learning (X1) and digital literacy (X2) are zero.
2. The value of the self-directed learning variable regression coefficient (b₁) of 0.623 explains that the increase in self-directed learning will improve the learning outcome of the Retail Business Management Lesson in Class XI BDP T.A. 2022/2023 (Y) by 0.623, assuming other independent variables.
3. Then the b₂ Digital Literacy variable regression coefficient of 0.362 explains the increase in the Digital Literation unit (X2) will increase the Retail Business

Management Lesson Learning Outcome in Class XI BDP T.A. 2022/2023 (Y) by 0.362, assuming other independent variables are fixed.

The value of the self-directed learning variable regression coefficient (b_1) of 0.623 explains that the increase in self-directed learning will improve the learning outcome of the Retail Business Management Lesson in Class XI BDP T.A. 2022/2023 (Y) by 0.623, assuming other independent variables.

Discussion

The Impact of Self-directed learning on Study for the result

The results of this study show a positive and significant influence between self-directed learning and learning outcomes. Thus, the first research hypothesis was accepted. The magnitude of the self-directed learning variable contribution to the learning outcome was shown by the result of a double linear regression analysis, which found a large effective contribution of 62.3%.

In self-directed learning, students have the initiative, with or without the help of others, to analyze their own learning needs, formulate their own study goals, identify learning sources, choose and implement appropriate learning strategies, and evaluate their learning outcomes. Self-directed learning gives students the freedom to explore and develop their own knowledge and can provide confirmation of new knowledge they have acquired. Students are invited to learn in a fun yet focused way. Independent learning followed by improved learning outcomes will be more qualitative, original, and lasting as students experience it in person, actively and participatively, by involving feelings, thoughts, and skills according to the learning objectives.

This study is in line with a study conducted by Ruslan, Rusli, and Rusdi (2018) entitled "The Influence of Self-Directed Learning and Mathematical Positioning on Student Mathematics Learning Outcomes." It is characterized by higher learning autonomy, followed by improved learning outcomes that provide greater benefits to students' cognitive, affective, and psychomotor skills in enhancing responsibility, improving skills, solving problems, and thinking creatively.

The Impact of Digital Literacy on Result Study

Based on the results of the research that has been done, it shows the positive influence and significance of digital literacy on learning outcomes. It can be seen from test-t results that obtain a t_{count} value of 2,910 and a degree of significance of 0.000 with significance < 0.05 . Thus, the second research hypothesis was accepted. The magnitude of the contribution of digital literacy variables to learning outcomes is shown by the result of a double linear regression analysis that found a large effective contribution as high as 36.2%.

In this study, the influence of digital literacy can be seen in the development of science and the use of technology or media (communication and information) by students of Class XI BDP SMK State 1 Field in their learning. It is characterized by the student's desire to improve science by leveraging technological advances.

The development of such technology provides an opportunity to acquire knowledge and information easily. This study is in line with the research conducted by Khoirul Latifah (2018) entitled "Digital Literacy and Self-Directed Learning in the Learning of Students of PBI IAIN Surakarta," which states that good digital literacy plays an important role in developing a person's knowledge of the subject matter by encouraging curiosity and creativity. Seeing the opinion of Kahar (2018:2), he argues that "digital literacy is the ability to use digital technology to understand, evaluate, use, and create information." This creates a source of reference knowledge available in digital form and accessible to obtain a variety of useful information to enhance

learning in schools. Stepping up learning will also automatically improve learning outcomes.

The Impact Self Direct Learning and Digital Literacy for Study Result

Self-directed learning and digital literacy together have a significant impact on retail business management lesson results in Class XI BDP T.A. 2022–2023. This is shown by the results of the F test, which obtained a value of $f_{\text{count}} > f_{\text{table}}$ $5,796 > 3,143$ and a significant dimension of α $0,000 < 0,05$.

Self-directed learning is better and more effective at involving students' learning independence in the learning process. This model provides enough space for students to build knowledge, develop their own abilities, work with their group to discuss, freely express opinions, respect each other and acknowledge the advantages of their friends, and build an atmosphere that cares for one another and supports the learning process, so that when done well, the results will be good too. It is useful to support the learning outcomes of students by accepting the learning process.

Besides, to improve learning outcomes, digital literacy is required. The development of information technology and the Internet has had consequences for students. Information can be obtained very easily. The consequence of this condition is the abundance of information, which sometimes creates difficulties for students in accessing the information they need. The ability to manage information properly and to distinguish between valid and invalid information is an impact of digital literacy. If the information consumed is of good value, then the results will be good too. So it is useful to support the learning outcomes of students in the work of the learning process.

The efforts to improve learning outcomes with self-directed learning and digital literacy are acceptable and well implemented by students of Class XI BDP SMK State 1 Medan T.A. 2022-2023. The third hypothesis is proven to provide information that self-directed learning and digital literacy together have a significant influence on the retail business management learning outcomes of Class X BDP State 1 SMK Field, which have been measured on the basis of the learning outcome indicators, namely the Middle Semester Examination of Business Retail Management Objects.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results of testing and discussion of the data collected on the impact of self-directed learning and learning outcomes on the study result of Pengelolaan Bisnis Ritel Grade XI BDP SMK Negeri 1 Medan 2022/2023 Year, the following conclusions can be obtained:

1. There is a positive influence and significance of self-directed learning on learning results in students of Grade XI BDP SMK Negeri 1. This shows that the higher the tendency of students to learn independently, the higher the learning result for them.
2. There is an influence of digital literacy on the learning results of students in Grade XI BDP SMK Negeri 1. This shows that the better the digital literacy of students, the higher the learning outcome.
3. There is a positive and significant influence of self-directed learning and digital literacy on learning outcomes in students in Grade XI BDP SMK Negeri 1. This means that student learning outcomes are influenced by self-directed learning and digital literacy.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the research that has been outlined and concluded, then there are some suggestions to improve the learning results. As for the advice given by the researchers, as follows:

1. In an effort to improve the learning outcomes of students, so that students are more enthusiastic in following and learning about self-management in learning and following the 4.0 revolution so that they can a better level of self-directed learning and digital literacy.
2. For the school in this case SMK State 1 Field, ahead of it to maintain the quality and quality of students so that later will produce graduates who are qualified and qualified.
3. For future researchers, the researchers suggest that it is better to do research by adding more variables that have not been studied in this study, so that further research is wider so that it can solve the problem of learning results. And then it is expected to do more extensive research using more population and samples so that the results of the research are more percentage.

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